

Cross-Modal Analysis of Spatial-Temporal Auditory Stimuli and Human Micromotion when Standing Still in Indoor Environments

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Abstract. This paper examines how a soundscape influences human stillness. We are particularly interested in how spatial and temporal features of a soundscape influence human micromotion and swaying patterns. The analysis is based on 345 Ambisonics audio recordings of different indoor environments and corresponding accelerometer data captured at the chest of a person standing still for ten minutes. We calculated the temporal and spatial correlation between the person's quantity of motion and the sound energy of the Ambisonic recordings. While no clear temporal correlations were found, we discovered a correlation between the spatial directionality of the micromotion and the sound direction of arrival. The results suggest a potential entrainment between the directionality of environmental sounds and human swaying patterns, which have not been thoroughly studied previously compared to the temporal or spectral features of indoor soundscapes.

Keywords: Environmental rhythms · Human micromotion · Spatial audio · Cross-modal analysis.

1 Introduction

Even when humans try to stand still, we always move slightly [7]. This is based on postural sway driven by continuous muscular activity in the legs combined with respiratory phases and involuntary postural adjustments [3]. We use the term *micromotion* to describe the smallest motion that humans can produce and experience, typically at a millimeter scale [6]. Together with meso-level (centimeter-scale) and macro-level (meter-scale) motion, micromotion has been studied as a phenomenon of embodied music cognition, playing an essential role in the studies of how humans perceive and interact with musical rhythms [11, 2].

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Proc. of the 17th Int. Symposium on Computer Music Multidisciplinary Research, London, United Kingdom, 2025

Fig. 1. Screenshots from the “fisheye” view from some of the 360-degree videos in the StillStanding dataset that is used for the analysis of relationships between soundscapes and human stillness.

The act of standing still reveals a rich tapestry of involuntary micromotion, which can be measured and analyzed to uncover patterns of embodied perception and environmental responsiveness, and that can be explained as part of a continuous action–perception loop between a human and the environment [4]. Past research has focused on how *musical* sounds affect humans when they are standing still. However, there are few studies on the effects of *non-musical* sounds, including everyday sounds in real-world environments.

This study examines the impact of soundscapes on body motion during intentional stillness in indoor environments, each with distinct sonic characteristics. While previous studies have mainly focused on the temporal and spectral features of indoor soundscapes, we have analysed the spatial (directional) information of soundscapes based on Ambisonics recordings. This is correlated with accelerometer data from a person standing still in each room. The goal is to gain a deeper understanding of a particular type of *sound–motion relationship* and how sound contributes to our sense of presence, balance, and spatial awareness.

Section 2 introduces some relevant concepts before describing the collection of our StillStanding dataset in Section 3. Then, we explore the dataset in Section 4 using cross-modal correlation analysis between the accelerometer data and the Ambisonics audio recordings. To avoid confusion in terminologies, we use the terms “sound”, and “motion” when describing the physical *stimuli*, “auditory” and “visual” to explain perception of such stimuli, and “audio”, “video”, and “accelerometer data” when describing recorded *data*.

2 Background

2.1 Human Micromotion

Previous studies have shown that micromotion patterns, such as respiration, pulse, and postural adjustments, can be affected by music of different genres,

tempi, rhythmic patterns, and spectral characteristics [3]. Furthermore, lab experiments have revealed that differences in music-related micromotion behavior are related to age, exercise level, social interactions [8], and level of empathy [21]. There have also been explorations into using micromotion mechanisms for artistic purposes [7, 5, 12].

2.2 Spatial-Temporal Stimuli

Architectural elements in indoor environments, such as light, color, natural views, sound, smell, and specific geometries, have been shown to have psychological and physiological effects [17]. Blinking indicator lights, ventilation hums, ticking clocks, and intermittent appliance sounds are examples of *spatial-temporal stimuli*. These stimuli are inherently dynamic, varying across both spatial locations and temporal patterns. Such stimuli are often processed subconsciously, yet they contribute significantly to spatial orientation and temporal awareness, particularly in complex environments [18]. Recent research has explored how such human-observable signals can be systematically captured and modeled using sensor networks and machine learning techniques, enabling applications in ambient intelligence [20] and integrating physical and cognitive ergonomics [13].

2.3 Environmental Rhythms

Our interest in spatial-temporal stimuli is from the observation that they may exhibit rhythmic structures, which we refer to as *environmental rhythms*. This is inspired by Lefebvre’s *rhythmanalysis*, positing that rhythms—defined as repetitive patterns in time and space—shape human experience [10]. Lefebvre proposes that everyday life is structured by natural (e.g., bodily cycles, day and night), social (e.g., work schedules, traffic), and technical (e.g., media, machines) rhythms. People attend to both cyclical rhythms (repeating, like seasons) and linear rhythms (progressive, like a workday). Lefebvre emphasizes that space is not static but produced and experienced through these temporal patterns.

2.4 Embodied Music Cognition

Lefebvre’s reflections on how time, space, and the body interact in everyday life resonate well with recent music cognition theories, which emphasize that music (and its rhythms) is inherently multimodal [11]. Rhythmic structures can arise from the integration of auditory and visual stimuli, such as synchronized sonic pulses and light flashes. More intricate rhythmic experiences emerge when auditory features—such as loudness, pitch, and timbre—correlate with visual attributes like color, brightness, and spatial positioning [19]. This expanded notion of rhythm underscores the intricate interplay between environmental stimuli and perceptual processes, suggesting that rhythm is not merely a musical construct but a broader phenomenon embedded in everyday sensory experiences.

Fig. 2. The recording setup used for data collection. The GoPro Max and the Zoom H3-VR were attached with a fixed relative direction on a tripod raised to chest level.

2.5 Spatial Audio and Ambisonics

Spatial audio refers to a set of audio technologies that enable immersive sonic experiences, closely mimicking how we perceive sounds in the real world [16]. Traditional speaker setups focus on either single-source-based listening (mono) or various types of “stereo” setups (often with two speakers) that create a “two-dimensional” sound field. Spatial audio, on the other hand, allows listeners to perceive three-dimensional depth and height, as well as the position and motion of sound sources. This enhances immersion in applications such as film, virtual reality (VR), augmented reality (AR), and immersive media.

Ambisonics is a full-sphere surround sound format that captures and renders sound in all directions around a listener [23]. While it is arguably still a niche protocol, commercial Ambisonics recorders now make it convenient to perform field recordings. Unlike *channel-based systems* (e.g., 5.1 or 7.1) that are designed for fixed speaker setups, Ambisonics is *scene-based*, allowing it to be decoded into arbitrary numbers and setups of speakers. This versatility makes it useful not only for audio playback but also for analytical purposes.

3 The sound–motion Subset of StillStanding Dataset

To investigate the impact of soundscapes on human micromotion, we utilized a subset of the *StillStanding* dataset, comprising 365 recordings of 10-minute standstill sessions, collected by the last author. The dataset comprises immersive audio and video recordings (Figure 1), sensor data from a smartphone, physiological data from a sports watch, and corresponding text descriptions.

3.1 Data Collection

Each 10-minute recording was taken during a daily standstill session, performed around noon, throughout 2023, in a different room each time. Recordings began

Fig. 3. A frame from the ‘.lrv’ video showing the “fisheye view” from the two lenses in the 360-degree camera. The mobile phone is hung around the person’s neck.

and ended with a clap for synchronization and to measure the room impulse response. After each session, the participant described the room and documented their subjective experience.

Recordings of the environment were made with a 360-degree video camera (GoPro Max) and an Ambisonics audio recorder (Zoom H3-VR) mounted in a fixed setup on a tripod (Figure 2). The standalone audio recorder was added to ensure high-quality audio recordings in a standard format. While GoPro claims that the Max camera can record “spatial audio,” its spatial audio format is non-standard, rendering it unusable for analytical purposes [15].

Environmental, motion, and physiological data were captured using an Android smartphone. Attached to a string around the neck, this phone captured swaying and micromotion from the upper body (Figure 3). The microphone and light sensors on the phone can also be used for environmental analysis. Sensor data from the phone was captured using the *Physics Toolbox Sensor Suite 1* (ver. 2023.01.21) by *Vieyra Software*.

The data collection focused on indoor spaces, while some recordings were made in semi-indoor environments, such as a bus shelter with only two walls and a ruin with walls but no roof. To avoid recording other people, most sessions were made in private rooms (e.g. cabins, bedrooms, or storage rooms) or public rooms without other people present (e.g. conference rooms, offices, or libraries).

3.2 Data Processing

Each recording session lasted for approximately 10 minutes and was trimmed to exactly 8 minutes to remove synchronization claps at the beginning and end, as well as postural adjustments that were irrelevant to the analysis. For the current

study, we rely on the first-order Ambisonics (FOA) audio recordings from the Zoom H3VR and accelerometer data from the mobile phone.

The Ambisonics audio files were synchronized with the other file types by manually identifying the timestamp of the beginning clap in each audio recording. This could then be aligned with the peak in the loudness measurement from the .CSV files recorded on the smartphone. Due to some erroneous recordings, we used a subset of 345 out of the 365 recordings in the analysis.

4 Sound and Motion Analyses

4.1 Temporal Sound–Motion Correlation

Previous experiments suggest a strong temporal correlation between human micromotion and *rhythmic* and *musical* sound stimuli. We were therefore curious to investigate whether a correlation exists in *irregular* and *non-musical* sound stimuli of indoor environments.

Fig. 4. Temporal correlation analysis of all samples. There is no clear linear correlation between the temporal changes of QoM and audio loudness.

We calculated the *quantity of motion* (QoM) as the root mean square (RMS) of the three accelerometer axes captured by the mobile phone sensors. The sound intensity level was recorded with the *Physics Toolbox Sensor Suite* on the same mobile phone. Then, the temporal sound–motion correlation was obtained by calculating the Pearson Correlation Coefficient (PCC) between the QoM sequence and the loudness sequence. Figure 4 shows the temporal sound–motion correlation of all StillStanding samples. Most recordings are very close to the r-value of zero, and only 36 out of 345 recordings have $p < 0.05$, regardless of

the average loudness (x-axis) or mean QoM of the session (color). The results suggest that there is no temporal correlation between the audio loudness and the QoM in the StillStanding sessions. The change in correlation suggests that the prevalent and structural music stimuli, i.e. rhythmic components, are necessary for the entrainment between auditory stimuli and micromotion.

4.2 Directional Audio Energy

The Ambisonics recordings allow us to investigate spatial correlations between body motion and environmental sounds. To that end, we first need to calculate the *directional audio energy* $E_{amb}[\phi]$. We do that in the following steps:

1. Setup a horizontal virtual speaker array $\phi = [-180^\circ, -175^\circ, \dots, 0^\circ, \dots, 175^\circ]$ with elevation of 0° .
2. Decode the Ambisonics signal to the speaker array with a mode-matching decoder: $x[\phi, n] = \mathbf{D}\chi[n]$, where $\mathbf{x}[\phi, n]$ are decoded virtual speaker signals, $\chi[n]$ is the B-format, first-order Ambisonics signal, and \mathbf{D} is the decoder matrix where each loudspeaker is represented by the spherical harmonics spectrum of a Dirac delta, expressed as Legendre Polynomials [22, 14].
3. The decoded virtual speaker signals are then windowed into a small frame, and the RMS energy of each is calculated: $E[\phi, m] = \sqrt{\sum_{n=0}^N x[\phi, m+n]^2}$, where $E[\phi, m]$ is the RMS energy at angle ϕ and time frame m , and N is the window size.
4. Finally, we calculate the overall audio energy $E_{amb}[\phi]$ by summing the maximum directional energy of each time frame: $E_{amb}[\phi] = \sum_{m \in M} E[\phi | \phi = \operatorname{argmax}(E[\phi, m]), m]$.

Figure 5 shows examples of the calculated directional audio energy maps of the StillStanding dataset. The energy difference between the FOA recordings in different directions is low, since most recordings in the StillStanding dataset primarily contain quiet background sounds between 40 and 70 dB SPL. Therefore, the sum of energy in each direction across all frames does not vary significantly. However, if we only add the energy of the maximum direction at each frame, as in step 4, the resulting array clearly shows the differences. The proposed method can effectively extract the overall characteristics of different indoor soundscapes, revealing distinct directionality patterns. The scale of energy also varies significantly among the samples, as SS#301 has the highest energy at around 0.7, while SS#276 reaches a value over 8.

4.3 Directional Acceleration Energy

We calculate the directional acceleration energy $E_{acc}[\phi]$ from the accelerometer data captured by the smartphone in the following steps:

1. Remove the average value of each acceleration axis to clear the offset.

Fig. 5. A collage of directional audio energy of 15 Ambisonics recordings from the StillStanding dataset. The examples are picked at an equal interval of days.

2. Convert the transversal acceleration points from cartesian coordinates to polar coordinates: $\theta[n] = \arctan(a_z[n], a_y[n])$, $r = \sqrt{a_z[n]^2 + a_y[n]^2}$, where θ is the angular coordinate, r the radial coordinate, n the discrete time-step, a_z, a_y the transversal plane accelerations (since the phone was hung horizontally).
3. For each angular bin of ϕ , sum the energy of all points within the range of 5° : $E_{acc}(\phi) = \sum_{\theta[n] \in [\phi - 2.5^\circ, \phi + 2.5^\circ]} r[n]$, $\phi \in [-180^\circ, -175^\circ, \dots, 0^\circ, \dots, 175^\circ]$.

Figure 6 shows examples of accelerometer data maps (green dots) and the calculated directional acceleration energy (blue bars). Usually, people tend to sway back and forth (anterior–posterior) due to the stabilization effects of the feet [9]. Thus, deviations from such an anterior–posterior swaying pattern may be due to environmental factors. As expected, Figure 6 shows that the scale of acceleration energy remains the same in most recordings, while a few, such as SS#031, have more motion.

4.4 Spatial Sound–Motion Correlation

After obtaining $E_{acc}[\phi]$ and $E_{amb}[\phi]$ for the 345 recordings included in the analysis, the Pearson correlation between the two arrays is calculated. Figure 7 shows a plot of the calculated directional acceleration energy (left) and directional audio energy (right) of one plot (SS#046). The spatial correlation between motion directionality and audio directionality is considerably higher than the temporal

Fig. 6. A collage of directional acceleration energy of 15 sessions of accelerometer data from the StillStanding dataset. The examples are picked at an equal interval of days.

Fig. 7. Spatial correlation analysis of SS#046, a session in a concert hall. **Left:** Plot of acceleration (green) and summed directional energy (blue bins). **Right:** Plot of directional audio energy calculated from the Ambisonics audio recordings.

correlation. The sample SS#046 was recorded in a foyer with a loud refrigerator. Here, the sound source is visualized in the right figure as the peak at 175° , and we can see that the spatial alignment between sound and motion is relatively high, resulting in a Pearson correlation of 0.63 and a p-value of 0.001.

Figure 8 shows the sound–motion correlations of all the 345 StillStanding recordings. More than half of the samples exhibit relatively high correlations, with positive correlations higher than the negative ones. This suggests that a correlation exists between the directionality of environmental sound and human micromotion. A positive correlation indicates an effect—possibly through an entrainment mechanism—between the soundscape’s directionality and the person’s swaying patterns. A negative correlation means that the micromotion is in the orthogonal direction of the sound source.

Moreover, when the average loudness exceeds 70 dB SPL—considered the boundary between quiet/normal loudness and slightly unpleasant/noticeable loudness [1]—there are no negative spatial correlation samples. This suggests that the swaying patterns are reinforced in the direction of the sound source. While the correlation factor remains unclear, the loudness level can be considered a potential factor that “reinforces” the positive correlation when it exists.

Fig. 8. Spatial correlation of all StillStanding samples.

5 Discussion and Conclusion

In this paper, we investigate the impact of spatial-temporal stimuli on human micromotion. This is based on correlation analyses of 345 environmental Ambisonics audio recordings with the accelerometer data from the upper body motion of a human subject standing still. We propose a method for computing the directional audio energy from First-order Ambisonics recordings, which can reveal the

directionality characteristics of indoor soundscapes. The temporal sound–motion analyses showed no clear correlations between temporal changes in the person’s quantity of motion and loudness. This suggests that when prevalent and structured auditory stimuli are not present, temporal entrainment to the rhythm also does not exist. On the other hand, the spatial sound–motion analysis between the directional audio energy and the directional acceleration energy suggests potential entrainment between the directionality of environmental sounds and the direction of human micromotion, in which the mean loudness level could be a potential factor that reinforces the entrainment.

We hope this paper will inspire further studies on the spatial qualities of indoor soundscapes, which have not been thoroughly investigated compared to their temporal or spectral qualities. Our future work includes in-depth studies of the factors that affect spatial sound–motion entrainment and other bodily reactions to the soundscapes, including heart rate and visual focus. We would also like to invite researchers from various fields, including acoustics, machine listening, and ethnomusicology, to utilize the StillStanding dataset for interdisciplinary studies related to indoor environment perception.

Data Availability. Source code and data used in the analyses are openly available at <https://osf.io/tys3z/>.

Ethics Statement. This work was conducted following the ethical standards of our institution. Personal data has been handled in accordance with the GDPR.

Author Contributions. JG: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Visualization, Writing—original draft, Writing—review & editing. JT: Supervision, Writing—review & editing. ARJ: Conceptualization, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Supervision, Writing—original draft, Writing—review & editing.

Acknowledgments. The Research Council of Norway supported this study through projects 262762 (RITMO), 324003 (AMBIENT), and 322364 (fourMs).

Disclosure of Interests. The authors declare that they have no competing interests in the contents of this paper.

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